

**HEAD OF CHILDREN'S INSTITUTION IN ORGANIZING THE WORK OF FORMING
MATHEMATICAL IMAGINATIONS AND BIG TEACHER'S PLACE. EDUCATORS
KNOWLEDGE DEGREE AND FORMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SKILLS**

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Abstract : This article discusses the role of the director of the children's institution and the senior educator in organizing the work of forming mathematical ideas, ways to improve the level of knowledge and skills of educators, as well as summarizing work experience and spreading it among pedagogues in kindergarten.

Key words : educator , work organize to do , children , mudira , big educator , skill , work experiences generalization .

Educator in person to positivity rely on to him to be placed high demand with together done to be increased in collectives good traditions , high responsibility spirit , friendly mutually help , creative initiative lives Such in the circumstances work now starting educator pedagogues to the collective fast and ease with absorbed goes

To the profession about adjectives many p in terms of of the educator to himself characteristic , character and temperament features depends will be Pedagogy to the activity known hereditary inclinations was talented only one person really and factor educator to be possible said thoughts there is .

Before school education in institutions Methodical the work forms

Methodical to work leadership duties done increase personnel with collective and individual work forms through done is increased . Collective the work to the shape pedagogical meetings enters Before school children in institutions pedagogical soviet about To the statute basically the following issues see exit can : « Children Kindergarten education — upbringing program » of execution about educators reports , experience exchange , thematic check of the results The price is advanced pedagogical the experience and in science new achievements in practice use and others Pedagogical of councils sure topic before school education institutions status and yearly in the plan in the eye caught to tasks depends without as follows themes to bring can

1. Mathematics in training of children thinking activities activation the work experience with sharing
2. Elementary mathematician imaginations in formation the game methods and interesting from exercises use the work experience with sharing
3. Children by to be mastered mathematician individual characteristics of knowledge .
4. Mathematics in training individual approach to children .

Mathematician concepts development level different in humans naturally will be His formation constant exercise to do Demand does These are exercises family before school from education starts . In the family parents if so , before school in education of course educator-pedagogue will be That's why for each one pedagogue to the child mathematician imaginations shaping pedagogy theory and of teaching modern pedagogical technologies (interactive methods, individual approach , independent to engage in to teach and etc.) and national independence ideas with armed to be need Theoretical in terms of full based on modern pedagogical technologies and modern information technologies today's in the day education to the process apply the most current to the matter became

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Methodical literature (special published in magazines articles , for example , before school education about study manuals , games and etc.) ;

Team and alone in order the work take go , advanced experience and of scientists thoughts Current in the day in children mathematician concepts formation problem scientific based on Methodical to the system have Theirs main elements purpose , content , methods , work tashil reach form and methods each other with organic depends . They are between main the goal the imagination to form is directed

Mathematician concepts form - human creative of activity whole purposeful done to be increased pedagogical is a process . His the goal is children only mathematics from knowing not but them to life preparation , their own in life places to find to receive help from giving consists of

In children mathematician concepts development of science main issues of the following consists of : In children mathematician concepts development level point of view in terms of second small , medium , large and to school preparation groups for conditions the plan justification ;

Mathematician concepts development school mathematics to learn preparation planning ; mathematician of concepts development ways and conditions work output ;

It's own in turn the world deep to know , to think development new methods learning such as tasks perform through will be solved . In children mathematician concepts of formation theoretical aspects psychological , pedagogical and other fundamental sciences based on will be created : Demonstration programmed documents (in children mathematician concepts formation according to instructions and etc.) ;

In children mathematician concepts development provider Methodical instructions to give G. Nedenko own in their work mathematician of abilities two level separate shows :

“ Normal medium ability ” (this ability initial school course appropriation for the ground was) and " from the middle high has been ability " , i.e mathematician knowledge easily in possession of issues mind the solution in finding manifestation to be is an ability .

Conclusion : This is the concept subjects and events some one environment symptoms according to differentiate or generalization is the result . For example , number, amount , section , correct line and or something . And the sign subject or of events to each other similarity , equality or differentiation denotative is a property . Subjects when you say objects mean is caught . Usually , objects known important and important didn't happen to properties have Important property only that's it to the object belongs to and this uncharacteristic object there is be can't get to properties it is said . of the object to existence effect who does not properties important didn't happen properties is counted . Object what means to know for his properties there is if so , then this object about concept there is is called Concept named as well as content and to volume have will be of the object all important properties together of understanding content tashil is enough One different important to properties have has been objects collection concept size tashil is enough So , the concept volume one concept with to be named possible has been objects there is also a collection . Mathematician concepts own in turn humanity collected

big the experience generalization as a result surface will come and material of the world the essence reflection but of real objects many properties the eye closed in case them idealization as a result harvest will be Mathematician concepts formation before school age the children mathematics to teach preparation of the school necessary from subjects one recognized as In children mathematician concepts formation theory and the main issue of the methodology in children mathematician concepts of formation didactic the basics work from exit consists of

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